

UZBEKISTAN STATE UNIVERSITY OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS
PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGY OF QUALIFYING FOR PARA ATHLETICS AT
THE STAGE OF MULTI-YEAR PREPARATION

Abdiev Sherzod Abdurahmonovich

Odilov Ruhiddin Fahriddinovicv

Kenjayeva Xilola Azizxodjayevna

Kushbakova Sevara Eshboyevna

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Abstract. *In this article, taking into account the level of preparation of para-athletes, based on the selection criteria, the issues of finding talented, promising para-athletes for multi-year training stages and increasing the possibilities of training qualified para-athletes are highlighted.*

Keywords: *Para-athletes, special physical training, general recovery, numbers and indicators of the training process.*

УЗБЕКСКИЙ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫЙ УНИВЕРСИТЕТ ФИЗИЧЕСКОГО
ВОСПИТАНИЯ И СПОРТА ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКАЯ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ
КВАЛИФИКАЦИИ ПО АТЛЕТИЧЕСКОЙ АТЛЕТИКЕ НА ЭТАПЕ
МНОГОЛЕТНЕЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ

Аннотация. *В данной статье с учетом уровня подготовки параспортсменов, исходя из критериев отбора, рассматриваются вопросы поиска талантливых, перспективных параспортсменов для многолетних этапов подготовки и повышения возможностей подготовки квалифицированных параспортсменов. выделены.*

Ключевые слова: *Параспортсмены, специальная физическая подготовка, общее восстановление, цифры и показатели тренировочного процесса.*

Relevance of the research: after the independence of our republic, the focus on adaptive physical education and sports at the level of state policy, especially the establishment of the Paralympic Committee, is of great practical importance in raising the young generation to become healthy and perfect people. To this day, in the modern sports complexes being built in our cities and villages, he regularly practices para sports and improves his health. Today, about 1 million children are engaged in more than 12 types of para sports in our country.

They grow up healthy, strong, brave and determined. The development of para sports serves as an important tool for the youth of our country to achieve physical and spiritual maturity. Through sports, the will of our children is being found, their lifestyle and outlook are changing. The success of our talented athletes in various prestigious competitions is increasing year by year, spreading the fame of our country to the whole world. Para athletics, included in the Paralympic program, is increasingly developing in our country and is recognized as one of the popular para sports among boys and girls. Today, the adoption of a number of regulatory and legal documents related to para sports in our country, the establishment of the Paralympic Committee in Uzbekistan is raising the development of para athletics to a new level in our country.

Today, 5,080 students in 254 sports schools, 1,020 students in 56 specialized schools, 280 students in 14 Olympic and Paralympic sports training centers, 312 students of Nukus and

Ferghana branches of UzDJTSU are expected to participate in sports in 12 Paralympic sports. But we found out during the research process that not all of them are talented in para athletics. Because we are witnessing the fact that the students allow the youth to participate in para-athletic sports.

When forming groups, coaches often form groups based on the recommendations of a secondary school student, so groups are observed to disperse within 2-3 months, and secondary selection criteria are not taken into account. A group is not formed based on 1 or 2 indicators, which negatively affects the effective training of para-athletes. As a result, young people studying for 2-3 years waste their precious time. Therefore, the development of selection criteria and the selection of students into groups based on these criteria increases the effectiveness of the training system of highly qualified para-athletes.

Therefore, the research conducted on the topic "Pedagogical technology of qualifying for para athletics at the multi-year training stage" is considered one of the urgent problems in the selection of para-athletes. The level of study of the topic. Today, the number of young people engaged in para sports is increasing day by day. Of course, this is a proof of the correctness of the reforms launched in our country. Currently, many specialists have been working on finding and selecting talented athletes among our young athletes, including V.B. Zelichenik, V.G. Verkshoshansky, M.N. Umarov, F.A. Kerimov, K.T. Shakirjanova, O. .V. Goncharovas are conducting their activities.

The purpose of the research: to increase the effectiveness of the selection of para-athletes based on pedagogical technologies for the multi-year training stage of para-athletics.

Tasks of the research: based on the purpose of the topic, we set the following tasks:

1. Studying, analyzing and summarizing scientific literature on the topic.
2. To study the qualification criteria for para-athletic athletics at the multi-year training stage.
3. Determining the physical development, level of preparation, and functional status of students according to their age.
4. Elaboration of topics for qualifying for multi-year training stages by age and level of training.

Organization and conduct of the research: The research has been carried out in 254 sports schools, 56 specialized schools, 14 training centers for Olympic and Paralympic sports, and branches of UzJTSU in Nukus and Fergana in our Republic.

The object and subject of the research: 254 sports schools, 56 specialized schools, 14 training centers for Olympic and Paralympic sports tours in our republic for 12 Paralympic sports tours, training groups of employees in the Nukus and Ferghana branches of UzJTSU, age of qualifying for multi-year training stages and pedagogical level of training development of technology and determining its effectiveness in pedagogical practice.

The scientific innovation of the research is to find talented and promising para-athletes for the multi-year training stages and to increase the possibilities of training qualified para-athletes, based on the developed criteria for selecting young people who are studying for the long-term training stages of the BSOs, taking into account the level of preparation of their physical development.

Scientific hypothesis of the research: It was assumed that the development of a new structure of criteria for selection of para-athletes for the multi-year training stages of the BSOs, taking into account the level of physical development, will serve to increase the efficiency of the system of training qualified para-athletes.

The scientific and practical importance of the research: development of pedagogical technology for qualifying stages of multi-year preparation and determining its effectiveness in pedagogical practice, strengthening the health of the growing young generation, attracting para-athletics to the sport and training reserve athletes.

Research methods.

The following methods were used to solve the tasks:

- To study and analyze the scientific and methodological literature on the development of pedagogical technology according to the age and level of preparation and determining its effectiveness in pedagogical practice;
- Monitoring and analyzing training processes;
- Pedagogical control tests;
- Pedagogical experience;

Summary

- 1. The interesting games and competitions organized by us in the study were very easy to attract the students of the SCHOOL to the research, because it was new for the students of the SCHOOL.
- 2. In the experiment, we observed the students who participated in each game and competition, and by analyzing the results, we classified them into the types of para athletics, and it gave its results.
- 3. In conclusion, we believe that interesting games and competitions will be of practical importance in raising interest in para-athletic athletes through this program, guiding them to sports and, most importantly, to love this sport from a young age, and in the future, world and paralympic champions will emerge from among them.

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